

Notes

Monoamine Oxidase Inhibitory and Anticonvulsant Activity of Some New 1-(Thiazol-2-yl)-2-Methyl-4-(Substituted Benzylidene)-5-Imidazolones

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Manuscript received 9 March 1979, accepted 4 August 1979

IMIDAZOLIDINONES have been reported to possess potent CNS depressant activity¹⁻². Anticonvulsant activity was also shown with some imidazole derivatives³⁻⁴. Recently 1, 2, 4 trisubstituted-5-imidazolones have been reported to possess monoamine oxidase (MAO) inhibitory and anticonvulsant activity⁵. Benzylidene derivatives are also reported to possess anticonvulsant and MAO inhibitory activity⁶⁻⁷. These observations, prompted the synthesis of 1-(Thiazole-2-yl) 2-methyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolones. The MAO inhibitory effects of imidazolones were investigated using rat brain homogenate. The anticonvulsant property of these compounds against pentylenetetrazole induced seizures was also determined.

The compounds were synthesized according to the scheme given below.

Experimental

1. Acetic acid was prepared by known method⁸.
2. 2-methyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-oxazolones were also prepared according to reported method⁹⁻¹⁰.
3. 1-(Thiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolones: The appropriate oxazo-

lone was heated with an equimolar quantity of 2-aminothiazole in an oil bath at 140°C for 1 hr. The jelly like mass which separated was recrystallized from appropriate solvent. The compounds synthesized are recorded in Table 1 and characterized by sharp mps, elemental analysis and I.R. spectroscopy.

Determination of monoamine oxidase inhibitory activity:

A spectrophotometric method was used for the determination of monoamine oxidase activity of rat

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Ar	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Cryst. solvent	Yield %
1		C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ Cl ₂ OS	110	Acetone and n-heptane	50
2		C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S	80	"	55
3		C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ Cl ₂ OS	95	Benzene/pet. ether	45
4		C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃ S	98	"	45
5		C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₃ OClS	105	"	55
6		C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS	102	"	60
7		C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃ S	100	"	55
8		C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S	107	"	50
9		C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ ClS	98	"	50
10		C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	85	"	45

mps were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Compounds were analysed for 'N' and % error in within limit.

* A part of Ph.D. Thesis

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TABLE 2—ANTICONSULSANT ACTIVITY AND MAO INHIBITORY ACTIVITY

Sl. No.	Protection%	Mortality after 24 hr. %	MAO inhibitory activity %
1	40	40	416.6
2	20	60	50.00
3	60	20	54.16
4	60	20	83.32
5	60	40	62.49
6	80	40	28.33
7	60	20	83.32
8	80	20	28.33
9	80	40	28.33
10	60	40	83.32

- Compounds are in same serial as in Table 1.
- Compounds were administered at the dose of 100 mg/kg intraperitoneally.
- Compounds were dissolved in propylene glycol, each experiment was done in duplicate and figures indicated the mean value at a concentration of 0.1 mM.

brain homogenate using benzylamine as the substrate. The benzaldehyde formed during oxidative deamination of benzylamine was estimated using a Hitachi-Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer at 250 μ m.

Male adult albino rats, weighing approximately 150-200 gm, were killed by decapitation. The brain was quickly removed and homogenized in 0.25 M sucrose using Potter-Elvehjem homogenizer. The final volume of the homogenate was 10% (w/v) of fresh tissue. Homogenization was done at 0.5°. The reaction mixture in a final volume of 2 ml consisted of 0.4 ml of phosphate buffer (0.5 M, pH 7.2) 1 ml of benzylamine HCl (0.1 M) and 0.2 ml of brain homogenate equivalent to 20 mg wet tissue weight and suitable aliquot of the compound solution to be tested. Compounds were dissolved in propylene glycol (100%) and used at a final concentration of 1×10^{-8} M. The reaction was started by the addition of substrate after a preincubation of 5 min at 37°C. After an incubation period for 30 min reaction was stopped by the addition of 1 ml of 10% perchloric acid and the precipitated proteins were removed by centrifugation. The optical density of the suitable aliquot of the supernatant was measured at 250 nm. The percent inhibition was calculated from the decrease in the optical density change.

Determination of anticonvulsant activity¹⁷:

Anticonvulsant activity was determined against pentylenetetrazol induced seizures in albino mice of

either sex weighing 25-30 gm. The mice were divided into group of ten, keeping the group weights as uniform as possible. All compounds were suspended in 5% aqueous gum acacia to give a concentration of 25% (w/v). The test compounds were injected i.p. into a group of ten mice, at a dose of 100 mg/kg. Four hrs after administration of compounds, the mice were injected with pentylenetetrazol (80 mg/kg). The animals were observed for 60 minutes for occurrence of seizures. Clonic spasm persisting for at least 5 sec was considered to be a threshold convulsion. Transient intermittent jerks and tremors were disregarded. Animals not exhibiting threshold convulsions during 60 minutes were considered protected. The number protected in each group was recorded and the anticonvulsant activity of compounds was represented in terms of percent protection. The mice were further observed for 24 hrs for recording mortality.

Results and Discussion

In this series, compound Nos 6, 8 and 9 showed maximum protection of 80% where as minimum protection was recorded in compound No. 2. It appears that presence of two phenyl ring markedly reduces protective ability. Less protection was seen in a di halo substituted compound, where as unsubstituted phenyl ring or a 6-methoxy substituted or *o*-methoxy *p*-chloro substituent appeared to increase the protection.

20-60% mortality was present. The minimum mortality of 20% was shown in animals treated with compound Nos. 3, 4, 7 and 8 maximum mortality of 60% was found in compound No. 2 which have two phenyl ring.

It appears that *o*-methoxy substituent is most effective affording having the highest protection and minimum mortality.

All these compounds inhibited monoamine oxidase the inhibition ranging from 28.33 to 83.32%. Compound Nos 4, 7, 10 were better inhibitors as against 6,8 and 9.

These observation also indicate that the presence of methoxy group increases biological activity.

No definite structure activity relationship can be established in this small series of compounds.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. S. Yajnik, Department of Anaesthesiology and Prof. K. P. Bhargava, Department of Pharmacology for their advice and encouragement. One of us is thankful to I.C.M.R., New Delhi for providing financial assistance (V.K.S).

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Protonation Reaction Between Cobalt Phosphate and Urea Nitrate in the Solid State

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Manuscript received 20 January 1979, revised 28 May 1979, accepted 6 October 1979

AFTER the establishment of the essentiality of cobalt for leguminous plants and nitrogen fixing bacteria¹, a lot of work has been done about the influence of micronutrients upon the availability of macronutrients to plants under different soil conditions. Cobalt and iron have similar ionic radii, charges, can replace each other and occur together in many geological materials. Acid soils containing iron phosphates is unavailable to plants because it can convert "available" phosphate to "unavailable" phosphate². To make iron or cobalt

phosphate available to plants especially in acid soils is therefore of considerable interest in soil chemistry. In the present investigation an attempt has therefore been made to study the protonation reaction between tribasic cobalt phosphate and urea nitrate on the lines reported by one of the authors in an earlier communication³, so as to ascertain the possibility of using urea nitrate for releasing phosphates of acidic soils containing iron or cobalt phosphate.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were BDH AnalaR grade. A series of mixtures were prepared by mixing 1 mole of $\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ with varying amounts of urea nitrate and each mixture was ground in an agate mortar for about an hour under dry conditions. The extent of availability of phosphate in the ground mixture was determined by methods reported earlier⁴.

Results and Discussion

The results indicate that the water solubility and citrate solubility (Table 1) of the phosphate in the various products obtained on grinding tricobalt phos-

TABLE 1—WATER AND CITRATE SOLUBLE P_2O_5 IN COBALT PHOSPHATE—UREA NITRATE MIXTURE

Cobalt phosphate to urea nitrate mole ratio	Total P_2O_5 %	Water soluble P_2O_5 %	Citrate soluble P_2O_5 %	Fraction of water soluble P_2O_5 %	Fraction of citrate soluble P_2O_5 %
1:0	38.71				
1:1	28.99	3.17	12.95	10.96	44.70
1:1.50	25.75	3.19	16.58	12.42	64.38
1:2.00	23.17	4.90	16.44	21.18	70.96
1:2.50	21.05	10.51	9.77	49.92	46.44
1:3.00	19.29	12.42	6.58	64.38	34.11
1:3.25	18.52	14.41	3.75	77.79	20.28
1:3.50	17.81	17.36	0.24	97.50	1.36
1:3.75	17.14	17.06	—	99.52	—
1:4.00	16.53	16.51	—	99.86	—

phate with increasing amount of urea nitrate gradually increases and decreases respectively. At the stage of 1 : 4 mole ratio cent per cent water soluble mixture is obtained.

The interaction occurs in two steps

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